

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE MAIN COMPONENT OF ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH COMPLETE DENTITION

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Abstract

Orthopedic rehabilitation of patients with complete loss of teeth is always associated with a change or restoration of the interalveolar distance, the optimal value of which has a significant impact on the functioning of the organs of the dental system. Reliable stabilization of prostheses ensures the correct fixation of the interalveolar distance and is the key to the normal state of the organs of the maxillofacial region.

Keywords: *complete removable denture, individual tray, functional impression*

The absence of teeth not only causes a violation of the chewing and speech function, but also causes a disproportion in the parameters of the facial skeleton of the skull, provokes psychological and personality changes, and violates the social tolerance of people.

Good fixation and stabilization, optimal functional and aesthetic effect can be achieved with the help of qualified performance of each of the stages of manufacturing complete removable lamellar dentures [1]. In solving this problem, the leading place is occupied by the question of how to obtain functional impressions, the accuracy and correctness of which determines the quality of the future denture [4].

The method of fitting an individual spoon on the edentulous lower jaw and obtaining a functional impression according to F. Herbst, who proposed to set the optimal boundaries of the spoon according to its displacement during functional tests, is widely used among orthopedic dentists. However, this method is ineffective in case of large atrophy of the alveolar process, since the functional tests proposed by Gerbst are standardized, do not take into account the individual characteristics of the patient's oral cavity and do not provide for the design of the outer polished surface of the prosthesis base in accordance with the contours of the movable anatomical structures adjacent to it.

To achieve optimal functional suction, it is necessary to accurately model the edges of the prosthesis, taking into account the anatomy of the prosthetic bed,

especially in the neutral zone, which has greater compliance. Therefore, the more accurately we determine this zone and position the edges of the individual tray when obtaining a functional impression, the higher the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment [3].

It has been established that both men and women need orthopedic treatment with the same frequency, and the need for this type of dental care increases with age. It has been determined that the average shelf life of removable dentures is 2–3 years [5, 10]. One of the fundamental factors for improving the quality of life and dental health of patients with complete absence of teeth is reliable fixation and stabilization of removable dentures, the achievement of which is often associated with significant difficulties in obtaining functional impressions, especially for beginners.

At present, it should be recognized that the main method of fixing complete dentures is a method based on the use of physical laws and anatomical features of the structure of the boundaries of the prosthetic bed. This method is called biophysical. For its implementation, it is necessary to create a rarefied space on the largest possible area. This becomes possible if the suction chamber is not a limited area, but the entire basis of the prosthesis. In this case, the closing valve is formed by the edge of the prosthesis and the mucous membrane of the neutral zone, a section of the mucous membrane with significant compliance and minimal mobility. Orthopedic rehabilitation of patients with

complete loss of teeth is always associated with a change or restoration of the interalveolar distance, the optimal value of which has a significant impact on the functioning of the organs of the dental system. Reliable stabilization of prostheses ensures correct fixation of the interalveolar distance and is the key to the normal state of the organs of the maxillofacial region [10]. To achieve fixation, it is necessary to obtain a clear display of the relief of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed, taking into account the functional state of the soft tissues of the prosthetic field in the manufacture of an individual impression tray. For this purpose, in our opinion, polyester impression masses are the most suitable. The materials have well-pronounced mucostatic properties, which is necessary when taking impressions for removable structures, when displacement or extrusion of the mucous membrane is undesirable, as well as high hydrophilicity, thixotropy and plasticity. Monophasic and one-stage imprint eliminates the possibility of deformation due to the difference in the coefficients of elasticity of different layers, and also greatly facilitates the work of the doctor and saves time. The method of fitting an individual spoon on the edentulous lower jaw and obtaining a functional impression according to F. Herbst, who proposed to set the optimal boundaries of the spoon according to its displacement during functional tests, is widely used among orthopedic dentists. However, this method is ineffective in case of large atrophy of the alveolar process, since the functional tests proposed by Gerbst are standardized, do not take into account the individual characteristics of the patient's oral cavity and do not provide for the design of the outer polished surface of the prosthesis base in accordance with the contours of the movable anatomical structures adjacent to it. To fill this gap in the method of obtaining a functional impression from the edentulous lower jaw, P. Tanrykuliev proposed volumetric modeling of the outer polished surface of the basis of a complete removable denture of the lower jaw. Later, many techniques were proposed for the design of the edges of an individual tray and obtaining a functional impression. Thus, some authors suggest using a material for relining complete dentures to decorate the edges of an individual tray before obtaining a functional impression, which, in our opinion, can have a negative effect on the tissues of the prosthetic field [6, 7]. Other authors suggest using a hand-kneaded silicone edging mass to shape the edges of individual trays, while adhesive pads are placed on the inner surface of the individual trays to create a space between the individual tray and the mucosa. Subsequently, the pads are removed and a functional impression is obtained with a medium-fluid, and then with a high-fluid silicone impression mass [2]. Still others suggest edging a rigid individual tray with heated wax and obtaining a functional impression with alginate group impression materials using functional samples [8]. In addition, there is a technique for obtaining a functional impression with a rigid individual tray using stop stops made of composite material to position the tray during edging of the edges with thermoplastic mass. The subsequent functional impression is obtained using the Impregum 3M ESPE polyester material [9].

The above methods have a number of undoubted advantages, however, in our opinion, they are largely labor-intensive. The appearance on the dental market of innovative impression materials with improved properties and devices for taking an impression creates the conditions for a faster process of forming the edges of an individual tray and obtaining a functional impression during orthopedic rehabilitation of patients with complete absence of teeth. We have accumulated many years of experience in the use of the Express XT Penta Putty impression mass for the functional design of a peripheral closing valve in the neutral zone due to its excellent mucostatic properties, which eliminates horizontal displacement of the mucous membrane and allows the use of high mucosal compliance in the neutral zone to form a closing valve. 3M's new ESPE "Express XT Penta H" A-silicone material, featuring even lower viscosity and longer working time, makes it possible to form the ideal closing valve for a complete denture. According to the proposed method, an individual spoon pre-fitted with Herbst samples is shortened along the borders by 3–4 mm and the edge thickness is reduced to 1–2 mm. Thanks to the Pentamix automated mixing system, high-quality and uniform preparation of the impression mass is carried out, as well as fast and uniform application to the borders of the impression tray. In this case, it is necessary to preliminarily apply an adhesive to the surface of an individual impression tray. After placing the spoon on the prosthetic bed, it is pressed against the mucous membrane and its edges are passively formed until the impression mass is structured, while functional tests are added to form the lingual edge, which makes it possible, under difficult clinical conditions, for prosthetics on the edentulous lower jaw to always achieve adequate boundaries of the basis prosthesis and optimal design of its outer surface. After structuring, the layer of the impression mass on the outer surface of the individual tray follows the contours of the movable anatomical structures adjacent to it, and the inner layer acts as a limiter-stopper for further positioning and creating a space between the individual tray and the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed. To obtain a refining functional impression, we use the corrective material "Express Ultra-light body", which has excellent fluidity and is distributed over the surface in a thin layer. The mass is produced in cartridges designed for convenient dosing and mixing with a Garant dispenser gun, which facilitates and speeds up its application to the impression tray. The applied corrective mass "Express Ultra-light body" flows well under pressure, filling the thinnest cavities when obtaining a corrective impression, while due to its good mucostatic properties, the need to perforate the impression tray to obtain decompression is eliminated.

CONCLUSION

This method of obtaining a functional impression minimizes the traumatic effect of the prosthesis on the oral mucosa, reduces the number of corrections, and therefore contributes to a faster adaptation of the patient to the prosthesis. In conclusion, it can be noted that despite the fact that the success of orthopedic treatment of patients with a complete absence of teeth depends on

the qualified implementation of all stages of prosthetics, the decisive role belongs to the creation of an effective closing valve, which is certainly achieved by obtaining a functional impression taking into account the neutral zone.

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